

Harappan Religion and Fire Worship

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Accepted: 30 Sep 2024 / Published online: 17 December 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032206>

Abstract

The Harappan Civilization, renowned for its urban planning and sophisticated technology, has also provided intriguing evidence of religious practices. While the nature of Harappan religious practice remains largely enigmatic, the discovery of fire altars at sites like Kalibangan, Lothal, Rakhigarhi etc. has sparked considerable interest in the possibility of fire worship as a central element of their religious beliefs. This article explores the existing archaeological data on fire altars, their architectural features, and potential ritualistic significance within the broader context of Harappan society.

Key Words: Fire-altar, fire worship, Kalibangan, Lothal, Rakhigarhi, Nausharo, linga worship.

Introduction

The prevalence of mother goddesses in the religious practices of the Harappan culture has been a recurring topic of discussion among archaeologists and researchers. Since its initial discovery, the worship of mother goddesses has been recognized as a significant aspect of Harappan civilization.

Notably, the initial excavations of Harappa and Mohenjodaro, the first two discovered cities of the Harappan or Indus civilization, yielded artifacts that were widely regarded as representative of the entire civilization. However, in the eastern region, the search for evidence was not as comprehensive, resulting in a limited understanding of the civilization's primary concentration along the extinct Saraswati or present-day Ghaggar-Hakra river. In the 1950s, Shri Amalananda Ghosh, the then Director of the Archaeological Survey of India, conducted an archaeological survey along the banks of the Ghaggar River. Several Harappan cultural centers have been discovered. Over the past century, gradual discoveries have revealed that the oldest and largest centers of this civilization are not only found on the banks of the ancient Saraswati River, but they also far outnumber those on the Indus River. Numerous new aspects of Harappan culture have been progressively uncovered.

One of the most significant topics in these discoveries is the religious identity of this culture. Previously, it was widely assumed that "Matrika worship" and linga worship were the exclusive and fundamental beliefs of this culture. However, the Gujarat and centres adjacent to the Saraswati river have challenged this limited belief. It appears that the so-called "Matrika worship" (although in some recent study a number of questions has been raised about the concept of so-called Mother goddess worship in the Harappan civilization) is absent from most centres of this culture. In this context, it is crucial to comprehend the unique characteristics of the religion of the ancient Saraswati contiguous region and the Harappan centres of Gujarat.

Fire worship

Archaeological evidence suggests the existence of fire worship and animal sacrifice rituals at various locations within the eastern and southern regions of the Harappan civilization. Specifically, certain Harappan cultural sites situated in present-day India exhibit two distinct modes of worship: (i) a fire-centric worship system and (ii) a form of animal sacrifice. Traces of these unique religious practices have been identified at significant centers such as Kalibangan, Banawali, Rakhigarhi, Rangpur, and Lothal. Notably,

Kalibangan

Kalibangan comprises three excavated mounds designated as KLB 1 (Citadel), KLB 2 (Lower Town), and KLB 3 (ritual site). KLB 1 features a platform on its southern side where a row of seven fire altars were discovered, with two altars exhibiting substantial remnants despite partial destruction. These altars contain clay stele and fragments of terracotta cakes. An urn filled with charcoal and ash was discovered south of the altars, suggesting its use in maintaining a sacrificial fire. A well is situated nearby, along with an elevated platform for bathing and a water channel. These features indicate the presence of a ritual bath associated with the “Yajna” ceremony. Notably, the remains of a wall were found behind the fire altars, suggesting that participants in the “Yajna” rituals faced east during the ceremonies (Lal et al., p. 6; 2015) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Row of seven fire altars (Kalibangan)

Archaeological evidence of animal sacrifice has been discovered at Kalibangan. A brick pit measuring 1.3 x 0.9 meters was found on a separate platform in the southern section of the citadel. Among the discoveries were burnt cattle bones, antlers, ashes, and charcoal (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Animal sacrifice (Kalibangan)

It is believed that some form of animal sacrifice took place here. A broken triangular terracotta cake discovered at the site, further supports the prevalence of this practice in Kalibangan. One side of the cake depicts a man leading an animal on a rope (Figure 3), while the other side features a figure with horns (Figure 4) resembling the horned deity inscribed on the renowned “Pashupati seal”. Archaeologists suggest that the animal is likely being brought for sacrifice to this deity.

Figure 3. Terracotta cake (Kalibangan)

Figure 4. Terracotta cake (Kalibangan)

In KLB 2 or Lower Town, where scholars believe commoners and merchants resided, nearly every house has been discovered with a fire altar (Lal et al., p. 186; 2015). A small mound designated as

KLB 3 at Kalibangan has not yielded any evidence of settlement. It is believed that this mound was used exclusively for religious rituals, such as sacrifices. While some fire altars are present, no particularly noteworthy findings have been made aside from the patterns observed. The coexistence of early and mature Harappan pottery in this mound suggests to archaeologists that these artifacts date to a period when the inhabitants of both phases coexisted. However, the archaeological evidence from Kalibangan unequivocally demonstrates that fire worship was a prevalent religious practice there. It is understood that the fire altars at Kalibangan, like those at other centers, were constructed during the mature Harappan phase. Ample evidence of fire altars and animal sacrifices with ash (Yajñabhasma?) has been found not only at Kalibangan but also at locations such as Banawali and Lothal.

Lothal

Rectangular and oval-shaped altars have been discovered at Lothal (Figures 5, 6). The earliest evidence of domestic fire worship at this location originates from a dwelling belonging to Phase IIA. Subsequently, during the third phase, a fire altar constructed of burnt bricks was constructed in a “public place”. Notably, a similar fire altar was also constructed along a roadway. It is believed by the excavator that this fire altar was likely constructed for the worship of a specific community. There is no evidence of animal sacrifice found at this altar, indicating that it was used for general fire worship. Traces of fire worship have been discovered in numerous households within the Lower Town. According to the excavating archaeologist, S. R. Rao, there is no indication of state-mandated fire worship at Lothal, but individual-level fire worship practices were quite prevalent (Rao, pp. 216–218; 1985).

Figure 5. Rectangular fire altars of Lothal

Figure 6. Oval-shaped fire altars of Lothal

A brick structure measuring 8 inches in depth and 2 feet 9 inches by 2 feet 6 inches in size was unearthed from the third phase of occupation at Lothal. Within this structure, burnt bones of cattle were discovered. Archaeologists have determined that this structure was used for animal sacrifice. According to the excavator, “ Animal sacrifice is also attested to by the evidence from Lothal. Over

here, in a house ascribable to phase III (mature Harappan) was encountered a mud platform with a mud-brick enclosure on it, the altar measuring 85 cm x 75 cm on plan and about 20 cm in depth. Within this enclosure there lay charred fragments of bovine bones, a carnelian bead and a disk-shaped pendant of gold, besides plenty of ash and charcoal. The excavator, therefore avers that ‘the platform must have been used as a sacrificial altar and the mud-brick enclosure as a sacrificial pit.’ (Rao, p. 218; 1985)

Banawali

Signs of fire worship have been uncovered at Banawali in Haryana (Fig. 7). Regarding an artifact found at this site, archaeologist Shri J.P. Joshi states, “At Banawali, inside an apsidal mud brick temple, the remains (also see fig. 7.5a and 7.5b) of a highly burnt terracotta stump with ash have been found. This shows that the Harappans at Banawali had even erected an apsidal temple over the fire altar. Besides this, in some houses fire altars have been found containing ash and burnt stump of a stele, cylindrical or rectangular in the centre of a pit. This is important evidence from the Sarasvati Valley, which has not yet been reported from the other sites of the Harappan Civilisation. At Banawali, the peepal leaf motif is seen in painted pots. Triangular, round, spherical, and mustika type of terracotta cakes are also available” (Joshi, p: 142; 2008). Archaeologist M. K. Dhavalikar stated that “The structure belongs to the Mature Harappan phase and can be dated to the later half of the third millennium. It is built of mud bricks conforming to the Harappan standard of 4:2:1. The altar is roughly oval, but half of it is broken. The entrance to the temple is also brick paved. Adjoining it, on the left, is probably a sacrificial pit.”

Figure 7. Structure of an apsidal temple at Banawali

Baluchistan and Sindh — Pirak, Mehrgarh, Nausharo, Amri

Pirak and Mehrgarh also provided evidence of fire altars. According to Dhavalikar, “A different type of fire pit occurred at Pirak in Balochistan, which was in all probability used as a fire-altar. It was built on a squarish mud brick platform and had a small cavity in the center having fire-dogs. Similar fire-altars were also encountered in the fourth-third millennium levels at Mehrgarh which had raised edges.” (Dhavalikar, p. 119; 2007).

Several structures, associated with fire, have been discovered in the excavations at Nausharo. The excavator of Nausharo described those structures as ‘fireplaces’. But the nature of the structures reminds us the Indian examples of fire-altars. According to the excavator, “Another constant feature in every house is the fireplace. Usually they are along the eastern walls of the open spaces, a rectangular mud-brick structure with two compartments (fig. 24.8): the northern compartment, which is square, contains a jar or a clay btm, and the southern one, rectangular, opens towards the south and is partitioned along its length; what is striking is the huge quantity of ashes which fill

this southern compartment and flows out of the opening. Like the walls and the water structures, they have also been reconstructed several times on top of each other. Next to them are clay containers which usually contain ashes and burnt debris, and thus seem to have been used as trash bins, while the function of the other built-in container was to store fuel and other things like terracotta cakes, used as heat conservers in the fireplaces. A first hypothesis – that the built-in containers were meant to be tandoors – is not relevant, as they are usually in unbaked clay and very seldom show traces of burning.

Another type of fireplace very often met with in those open areas is a round fire-pit, either simple and rather small (diam. 35 cm) or large (diam. 1 M). Some are roughly built in a way which recalls those of Period I C with their central pillar supporting an upper chamber, as those found at Lal Shah (C. Jarrige et al. 1994: tenth season). They are also found in Period II, but rough imitations made of unfired bricks in Period III contain a vertical brick which was coated with clay in order to look round” (Jarrige, p. 288; 1994).

Moreover he also reported that traces of fire altars were found too in the pre-Harappan level of Amri.

Figure 8. 'Fireplace' (Nausharo)

Animal sacrifice

Several signs of fire worship have also been found from the mature phase of Rakhigarhi in Haryana (Nath, p. 44; 1998; 48; 1999). Besides this, examples of animal sacrifices have also been discovered at Kalibangan and Lothal. In the words of the archaeologist, “There is plenty of evidence of rectangular pits with signs of burning and the presence of bones inside. In one case, there was a brick placed vertically in the center of the pit. Some of these Rakhigarhi fire altars or sacrificial pits had shapes other than the usual rectangular type. In one case, it has been called ‘heart-shaped,’ while in the case of another, a semi-circular central projection has been noticed on its north and south sides” (Chakravarti, p. 159; 2006).

Rakhigarhi and Rangpur

Archaeologists have discovered various types of fire-altar from Rakhigarhi (Fig. 9). From all the phases at Rangpur, several evidences of fire worship has been recovered (Rao, p. 47; 1963) (Fig. 10).

Figure 9. Various types of fire-altars of Rakhigarhi

Figure 10. Fire altars of Rangpur

Vagad

Four fire-worship related structures have also been discovered at Bhagad in Gujarat (Srinivasan P. 122; 2011). According to J. P. Joshi “Vagad is a rural Harappan site locally known as Kelvo Timbo. It is located to the south-east, at a distance of about 1.5 km, within the vicinity of Vagad village on the right bank of the Bhalar river in Dhanduka Taluk of District Ahmedabad in Gujarat. The single-culture site with five layers is divided into two sub-periods. It has yielded evidence of four altars besides ter- racotta and stone weights; jars buried under the floors of the houses; pulley-shaped ear ornaments; partially ground and broken celt and graffiti on pots. The four circular clay-lined ire pits on a slightly raised platform are significant. The platforms are on the floor level of period IA Mehta and Sonewane recorded three bigger ones with sagging bases that were dug in the north, south and western portions of the trench. Their diameters are 1 m, 1.45 m and 1.30 m respectively. They were arranged in a triangular form at an approximate distance of about 90 cm between them. A fourth fire pit, cylindrical in shape, having a diameter of 40 cm, is placed a little

inside, between the southern and western pits. All of them were internally neatly plastered with cow-dung paste mixed with fine clay. These pits contained ash, possibly of cow-dung cakes. In the absence of bone or any kind of industrial material, these pits appear to have been used for some kind of ritualistic purpose.” (Joshi, pp. 143—146; 2008).

Nageshwar

A structure measuring 165 cm has been discovered from the mature Harappan phase at Nageshwar in Gujarat. In the middle of it is seen a clay stele like Kalibangan. A large amount of ash was discovered inside the structure and it was found that the walls of the structure, 65 cm deep, were highly burnt by a very high temperature fire. Archaeologists believe that it was a place for lighting high-flame fires (Joshi, p. 143; 2008).

Linga worship

Furthermore, some artifacts of Linga Puja have been discovered from several centers. Sri M.S. Bhats identified some artifacts from Harappa as examples of Linga Puja. But clear evidence of this is found from Kalibangan. A similar image of the linga and yonipatta symbol worshipped today has been recovered from the late Harappan phase at Kalibangan (Fig. 11) (Lal et al., pp. 1247-1249; 2020).

Figure 11. Linga with yonipatta from Kalibangan

Harappan and Vedic fire worship

A brief debate exists regarding the Interpretation of fire altars or fire pits discovered in the context of the Harappan civilization. The question is whether these structures represent examples of Vedic yajnas or sacrifices. It is crucial to recognize that the Vedas and the Vedic world primarily constitute a literary construct, lacking a precisely definable timeframe. Linguists generally consider the Rigveda to be the oldest form of Vedic literature. While the Rigveda mentions the term “Yajurvedi,” it does not provide detailed descriptions of its construction. Such details are found in various branches of Vedic literature from a much later period, including the Shrutasutras, Grihyasutras, and Brahmanas etc. These texts are estimated to have been composed around 1000 BCE or later. Therefore, comparing or contrasting archaeological remains dating back more than 1500 years with literary descriptions from 1000 BCE or later would be an unreasonable endeavor. Notably, evidence suggests that during the mature Harappan period, a ritual centered around fire gradually developed, even depicting sacrificial animals tied up in sacrifices. It is well-known that as a religious practice emerges within human culture, it progressively accumulates ceremonial formalities and regulations, becoming increasingly intricate. There is no reason to believe that the

process of fire-based worship is an exception. During the early to mature Harappan cultural phases, when fire worship gained prominence, the intricacies of the rules were incorporated much later. Consequently, we currently lack sufficient evidence to definitively determine whether the fire altars of the Harappan civilization are Vedic or non-Vedic. However, attempting to ascertain the nature of Harappan civilization's fire worship based solely on literary descriptions from over one and a half millennia later would be highly unrealistic. Instead, it is reasonable to propose that the fire altars and indications of fire worship discovered during the mature Harappan phase represent the earliest traces of Vedic rituals, the rules and details of which are created in much later times.

Conclusion

Fire worship and animal sacrifice occupy a special place in the discussion of the Harappan civilization. However, we must remember that this ritual was not equally popular among various centres of the Harappan civilization. Some scholars believed that fire worship was an important part of religious practices in the eastern and southern regions (mainly Rajasthan, Haryana, Gujarat) of the Harappan culture, distinct from the regions near the Indus. However, our analysis reveals substantial evidence of fire worship in the western regions as well.

The discovery of fire altars at Harappan sites like Kalibangan and Lothal has sparked considerable debate among archaeologists and historians. While these structures, often characterized by raised platforms or enclosed spaces, are undeniably linked to fire, their precise function and significance within the Harappan context remain elusive.

A primary challenge in interpreting these fire altars lies in their chronological placement. Many of these structures are associated with the mature phase of the Harappan civilization. This temporal discrepancy raises questions about whether fire worship was a core component of the early Harappan religion or if it was an imported practice.

To fully comprehend the role of fire altars in Harappan civilization, more extensive excavations, coupled with interdisciplinary research, are necessary. By carefully examining the context of these structures, their relationship to other architectural features, and the associated artefacts, archaeologists may be able to piece together a more accurate picture of fire worship within this ancient culture.

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